

Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners and their Academic Performance

Josef C. Edar¹, Antonieta C. Olores²

¹Lanot Elementary School, Department of Education, Philippines

²Faculty, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

Corresponding Email: josef.edar@deped.gov.ph

Received: October 27, 2025

Revised: November 20, 2025

Accepted: November 28, 2025

ABSTRACT

Many factors can impact the academic performance of learners. One of these is tardiness. It may become a habit among some learners that can lead to more serious problems, such as a poor learning process. This study aimed to determine the factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners and their academic performance. This study employed a descriptive research design, using a self-made research instrument, to assess the degree to which factors affect the tardiness of 102 Grade 7 learners. The results revealed that most respondents were female, had many siblings, lived farther from school, and lived with parents who had higher educational backgrounds. Overall, the degree to which factors affected the tardiness of Grade 7 learners was low. The level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners was satisfactory. There was a significant difference in the degree to which factors affected the tardiness of Grade 7 learners across three areas when compared according to their sex and parents' highest educational attainment. Moreover, a significant difference was found in the academic performance level of Grade 7 learners when comparing them by sex and their parents' highest educational attainment. Further, a significant relationship was found between the degree of factors affecting the tardiness and the level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners. Thus, addressing learners' tardiness requires a comprehensive and collaborative approach that involves educators, parents, and stakeholders.

Keywords: Academic Performance, Grade 7 learners, tardiness

How to Cite:

Edar, J. C., & Olores, A. C. (2025). Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners and their Academic Performance. *Global Journal of STEM Education & Management Research*, 1(1), 46-60. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17750502>

Licensed under **Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International License**.

INTRODUCTION

Tardiness is a significant barrier to academic success, affecting not only individual students but also the broader school environment and society. It is often linked to indiscipline and is seen as a behavior that can hinder the achievement of educational goals. Students who skip class without valid reasons are more likely to experience negative consequences in their learning, with tardiness being described as a major impediment to both personal and academic development.

According to recent surveys, student tardiness and absenteeism are pressing concerns in schools, with approximately 30 percent of public-school principals reporting them as major issues—higher than other disciplinary problems such as vandalism or theft. Tardiness is notably higher on certain days, like Fridays, creating challenges for teachers in meeting learning objectives. Factors influencing student tardiness include family circumstances, individual student characteristics, and school-related conditions, highlighting the complex nature of the problem.

Habitual tardiness and absenteeism are strongly associated with poor academic performance. Students who frequently miss classes struggle to keep up with lessons and school activities, impacting their holistic development and ability to connect previous learning with new concepts. In the research setting, around 12 percent of students are regularly tardy or absent, with common causes including financial difficulties, peer pressure, distance from school, lack of interest, and habitual behavior. Addressing these factors is critical for improving student attendance and overall academic achievement.

From the above issues, the researcher felt the urgency and was motivated to deepen her knowledge and understanding of student tardiness, in the sincere hope that the findings could address the problems and serve as a foundation for proposing interventions and future research.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine the degree to which factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners and their level of academic performance in a public secondary school within a large-sized schools' division in Central Philippines for the school year 2024-2025. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners according to the area of student-related factor, family-related factor, school-related factor; 2) the level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners in the first and second quarters of the school year 2024-2025; 3) the level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners when grouped according to the variables; 4) the significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 students when grouped and compared according to the variables; 5) the significant difference in the level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners when grouped and compared according to the variables; and 6) the significant relationship between the level of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners and the level of academic performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learners' academic performance is essential for producing high-quality graduates who contribute to a country's social and economic development (Olufemi, Adediran, & Oyediran, 2018) and is influenced by a combination of personal, familial, and environmental factors. Specifically, key determinants include learners' backgrounds, parental support, availability of learning resources, and the quality of the learning environment, including teacher competency and access to teaching materials (Rabia, Mubarak, Tallat, & Nasir, 2017; Abaidoo, 2018). Moreover, improved reading skills and strong personal motivation enhance academic outcomes, while active parental involvement further supports higher performance (Epeçan, 2018; Shahzad et al., 2020). Academic performance refers to the knowledge and skills gained by learners, typically assessed through continuous assessments or examinations (Leander & Fabella, 2020), and is influenced by intellectual ability, motivation, study habits, self-esteem, and teacher-learner relationships (Perocho & Bantolo, 2023). In addition, parental involvement plays a crucial role, as parents provide support and opportunities at home that complement school assessments, particularly for younger or full-time dependent learners (Orillosa, 2015). Academic performance is also affected by demographic, family, and school-related factors, including quality of instruction, availability of learning resources such as textbooks, libraries, laboratories, and meals, as well as student attendance and engagement (Lansangan et al., 2015; Kalagbor, 2016; Tani et al., 2019). Furthermore, studies show that individual learner characteristics, such as learning preferences, daily study hours, gender, and marital status, can impact achievement, while some factors like class size, age, residential area, and family income may have limited influence (Alfifi & Abed, 2017). Consequently, studies on learners' academic performance indicate that it is influenced by a combination of learning skills, parental support, learning environment, and personal and school-related factors (Anhao, 2022; Albarico et al., 2023). For instance, Anhao (2022) found that the degree to which these factors affect performance varies significantly with parents' educational attainment, family income, and the learner's sex, while Capinding (2021) noted that most students achieve fair to satisfactory grades, and age, sex, and educational environment showed no direct relationship with performance. Overall,

academic performance is shaped by a mix of home, school, and personal conditions, with learners encountering multiple challenges that can hinder their achievement.

In addition to these factors, learners' tardiness has become a widespread and persistent issue that negatively affects academic performance, classroom participation, and overall learning outcomes (Caroro et al., 2017; Villaneva et al., 2023). Despite proximity to school, students who arrive late miss critical instruction, disrupt lessons, and distract peers, compromising both their own and classmates' learning experiences (Gano et al., 2024). Notably, learners' tardiness is influenced by a combination of student, family, and school-related factors. Student-related causes include lack of motivation, behavioral issues, disinterest in studies, and sleep deprivation, which can disrupt learning and peer interactions (Balkis, 2016; Sahibzada, 2020; Whitney & Liu, 2016; Goodwin, 2020; Persky, 2018). Family factors, such as broken homes, low parental involvement, financial difficulties, and household responsibilities, can further increase the likelihood of lateness (Komache & Ossu, 2016; Moore et al., 2021; Collier, 2016). School-related contributors include ineffective teaching, poor discipline, bullying, and unfavorable school climate, which can discourage attendance (Ocak et al., 2017; Baier, 2016; Qureshi & Ahmed, 2019). Moreover, external conditions, such as distance from school, poverty, and health emergencies, as well as students' late-night activities, exacerbate the problem (Odebode, 2019; Cromey & Hanson, 2020).

Furthermore, learners' tardiness is influenced by a wide range of internal and external factors that impede punctuality and class attendance, including household responsibilities, long travel distances, transportation issues, poor time management, lack of discipline, low motivation, negative mindsets, and poor role models (Hamzar, 2020; Adegunju et al., 2019). Studies categorize these factors into three main groups: school-related factors, such as teacher attitudes, school environment, and instructional practices; home-related factors, including parental attitudes, home practices, and distance from school; and personal factors, such as health issues, interest, and motivation levels (Hamsa, 2020; Hamza et al., 2020). In addition, demographic and socio-economic variables, such as gender, age, family size, parental education, religion, and health conditions like anemia, also correlate with higher absenteeism and lower academic performance (Harisha et al., 2016). Causes of tardiness are multifaceted, including student-related factors such as lack of sleep, poor time management, and peer influence; family-related factors such as low parental involvement, household responsibilities, financial difficulties, and home conflicts; and school-related factors such as negative peer behavior, poor classroom environment, inadequate seating, and infrastructural challenges (Colinares et al., 2017; Moldero et al., 2024). As a result, habitual tardiness fosters negative attitudes and behaviors, which can impede academic progress, reduce engagement, and contribute to long-term issues such as academic failure and increased dropout rates, making it a chronic problem in both private and public schools.

Finally, studies on learners' tardiness and absenteeism reveal that multiple factors influence punctuality and school attendance, with personal, family, environmental, and institutional elements all playing roles. Key contributors include distance from home to school, transportation, time management, classroom environment, peer influence, socio-economic conditions, parental support, and personal motivation (Villanueva et al., 2023; Moldero et al., 2024; Salao, 2021; Abdullah, 2020; Polvorido, 2019; Sabado et al., 2024). While some studies note differences by gender, age, or school level, most indicate that demographics do not significantly affect the underlying causes of tardiness. Learners who are frequently late or absent tend to have lower academic performance, often influenced by their learning environment, parental involvement, peer pressure, and socio-economic constraints. Therefore, these findings underscore the importance of targeted interventions, such as creating dynamic learning environments and addressing logistical and motivational barriers, to reduce tardiness and absenteeism and improve academic outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employs a descriptive research design to determine the degree to which factors affect the tardiness of grade 7 learners in relation to their level of academic performance in a public secondary school within a large-sized schools' division in Central Philippines for the school year 2024-2025. Descriptive research is valuable in providing facts on which scientific judgment may be based in assessing the present study. Furthermore, a descriptive design is appropriate for studies that aim to discover what prevails in the present conditions, practices, held opinions and beliefs, processes, and effects, as well as developing trends (Manjunatha, 2020). This study design employs a scientific approach that involves observing and characterizing a subject's behavior without any form of interference (Siedlecki, 2020). The researcher believes that the descriptive research design is the most suitable for the present study, as it aims to gather information about the characteristics within the study and helps in making informed professional judgments and recommendations.

Study Respondents

The respondents in the study will be the 102 grade 7 learners who are officially enrolled during the 2024-2025 school year. Since the total number of respondents was manageable, purposive sampling will be used. Purposive sampling is a type of non-probability sampling in which researchers use their discretion to select study participants from the population, as described by Ames et al. (2019). Researchers use purposive sampling to reach a specific subset of people, as all survey respondents are chosen based on a predetermined profile.

Instruments

This study employed a self-designed questionnaire to collect data, divided into two parts: Part I gathered respondents' profiles, including sex, number of siblings, distance from home to school, and parents' highest educational attainment, while Part II assessed the degree to which student-, family-, and school-related factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners, comprising 30 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 ("almost never") to 5 ("always"). The instrument's validity was ensured through face and content validation by three expert validators—teachers with master's degrees in education, mathematics, and special education—whose recommendations were incorporated into the final version. Using the interpretation scale of Excellent (4.04–5.00) to Poor (1.00–1.75), the instrument achieved an average validity rating of 5.00, indicating it was highly valid. Reliability was established via Cronbach's Alpha to assess internal consistency, with a pilot test administered to 30 Grade 7 learners outside the study sample; the computed alpha for parental involvement was 0.873, demonstrating a statistically significant and acceptable level of reliability, confirming that the instrument consistently measures the intended constructs.

Data Gathering Procedure

To facilitate the smooth conduct of the study, the researcher employed the following procedures. A letter of request was submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent for approval to conduct the study. Upon approval, a letter of request was also given to the head of the subject school. After securing approval for the second request, questionnaires were administered to target respondents. The data gathered from the respondents' responses were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. SPSS was used in the computer processing of encoded data.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 employed a descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree to which factors affected the tardiness of grade 7 learners.

Objective No. 2 employed the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to assess the level of academic performance among grade 7 learners.

Objective No. 3 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of academic performance of grade 7 learners when grouped according to the variables.

Objective No. 4 employed a comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to identify significant difference in the degree to which factors affect the tardiness of grade 7 learners when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Objective No. 5 employed the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to identify the significant difference in the level of academic performance of grade 7 learners when grouped and compared according to the variables.

Objective No. 6 employed a relational analytical scheme and Spearman's rho to identify the significant relationship between the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of grade 7 learners and their academic performance level.

Ethical Consideration

To ensure the protection of study participants, the researcher prioritized the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity. In this study, for voluntary participation, the researcher asked respondents to sign or agree to a consent form by filling out a blank line/data entry slot with their initials or an alias. Consent from the parents of the respondents was also solicited. After they sign or agree to the consent form, they remain free to withdraw at any time without providing a reason. To obtain informed consent, the study ensured that participants were fully informed about the

risks and procedures involved in the study. The researcher avoided placing participants in situations that could put them at risk of injury to minimize the danger. If this happens, the participants can decline to answer all the questions and may withdraw their participation at any time. For confidentiality, the researcher ensured that participants' identifying information would not be disclosed to anyone not directly involved in the study. Furthermore, to maintain the anonymity of the respondents, they used an alias or initial to conceal their identity from the researcher and other participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1

Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners according to the Student-Related Factors

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>I am tardy in class because...</i>		
1. I am not interested in going to school.	1.78	Low Degree
2. I sleep late at night.	3.05	Moderate Degree
3. I get easily bored during class hours.	2.52	Moderate Degree
4. I always got sick (e.g., toothache, headache, fever).	2.46	Low Degree
5. I often feel exhausted from attending school.	2.10	Low Degree
6. I did not wake up early.	2.57	Moderate Degree
7. I did not study and make assignments the night before.	2.45	Low Degree
8. I have not eaten my breakfast.	2.50	Moderate Degree
9. I have no money to buy my snacks.	2.26	Low Degree
10. I got fond of playing games on my mobile phone.	2.89	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	2.46	Low Degree

Table 1 presents the degree to which factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners area related to student-related factors. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 2.46, interpreted as a “low degree.” This suggests that the learners’ attendance in school was less likely to be affected by their personal issues.

Investigating further, respondents reported a lowest mean score of 1.78 on item 1, stating, “I am not interested in going to school,” and interpreted it as a “low degree” of interest. On the other hand, the highest mean of 3.05 was observed for item 2, which stated, “I sleep late at night,” and is interpreted as a “moderate degree.”

The finding implies that the main reason for learners being tardy in the classroom is their tendency to stay up late at night. Some reasons learners sleep late include using Facebook and Messenger, playing mobile games, and completing their assignments and homework. Lack of sleep will lead learners to struggle to concentrate on lessons and lose their ability to succeed academically. This struggle not only affects their classroom performance but can also have long-term implications for their overall well-being. Therefore, both teachers and parents must encourage healthier nighttime routines that promote adequate rest and enhance academic success.

The results align with those of Adegunju et al. (2019), which revealed that the factors responsible for learners' lateness in elementary schools are going late to bed, poor preparation for school, the distance of school from home, a high level of poverty, peer pressure, and single parenting, among others. Cromey and Hanson (2020) also reported that most students incurred tardiness and were unable to wake up early because they were unable to sleep on time; some were engaging in multiple activities at night, particularly household chores. Some were having their reviews late, but mostly kept themselves busy, wasting time on the internet, chatting with friends, and texting.

Table 2

Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners according to the Family-Related Factors

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>I am tardy in class because...</i>		
1. My parents asked me to do household chores.	2.92	Moderate Degree
2. My parents asked me to take care of my younger siblings.	2.74	Moderate Degree
3. My parents cannot afford to buy school supplies and other materials needed in school.	2.20	Low Degree
4. I experience domestic violence at home.	1.88	Low Degree
5. My parents are always quarrelling.	2.06	Low Degree
6. My family is not financially stable.	2.43	Low Degree
7. My parents cannot afford to pay for my fare to attend school.	2.20	Low Degree
8. My parents rarely attend meetings related to my school activities.	2.05	Low Degree
9. My parents do not provide us with nutritious food, so we lack the energy to attend school.	1.94	Low Degree
10. My parents do not motivate us to do better in school.	1.83	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.22	Low Degree

Table 2 presents the degree to which factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners area related to family factors. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 2.22, interpreted as a “low degree.” This suggests that the respondents' tardiness was not solely due to family problems.

Analyzing further, respondents reported a lowest mean score of 1.83 on item 1, stating, “My parents do not motivate us to do better in school,” and interpreted it as a “low degree” of agreement. On the other hand, the highest mean of 2.92 was observed for item 2, which states, “My parents asked me to do household chores,” and is interpreted as a “moderate degree.”

The results imply that the most prevalent family-related issue causing learners' tardiness was household chores. Some parents assign household chores even when their children have classes during the day. Hence, learners may struggle with time management, particularly in prioritizing responsibilities such as household chores and attending classes. This struggle with time

management can lead to conflicts between fulfilling family obligations and maintaining academic commitments. As a result, learners may frequently arrive late to class due to their responsibilities at home.

The finding aligns with that of Colinares et al. (2017), who reported that at-home responsibilities, stressful family events, conflicting home and school priorities, low parental involvement, and unstable housing are family-specific factors that can cause students to miss school and may lead to the development of chronic tardiness.

Table 3

Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners according to the School-Related Factors

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>I am tardy in class because...</i>		
1. Our classroom is hot and uncomfortable.	2.45	Low Degree
2. My classmates always bully me because of My physical appearance.	2.11	Low Degree
3. Our classroom is crowded and noisy.	2.72	Moderate Degree
4. My teacher always scolded me whenever I was late going to school.	1.92	Low Degree
5. I cannot understand how my teacher delivers the lessons.	2.24	Low Degree
6. The school location is far from our home.	2.76	Moderate Degree
7. No strict penalties for students' tardiness.	2.24	Low Degree
8. Our school lacks learning materials for us to study.	2.18	Low Degree
9. Our school lacks sports or recreational equipment for us to play.	2.15	Low Degree
10. I have no friends in school.	2.19	Low Degree
Overall Mean	2.30	Low Degree

Table 3 reveals the degree to which factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners, an area related to school-related issues. The respondents obtained an overall mean score of 2.30, interpreted as a “low degree.” This suggests that school-related problems are less likely to impact learners’ tardiness.

Examining the table further, respondents assessed a lowest mean score of 1.92 on item 4, stating, “My teacher always scolded me whenever I was late going to school,” which they interpreted as a “low degree.” On the other hand, the highest mean of 2.76 was observed for item 6, which states, “The school location is far from our home,” and is interpreted as a “moderate degree.”

The finding implies that school location was the central issue of why learners come to school late. Many learners are having difficulty getting a ride early in the morning, particularly in the rainy season. Hence, some learners tend to walk to school, which causes them to be late or miss their first-period class. This affects their attendance and impacts their overall academic performance.

The finding is supported by Villanueva et al. (2023), who reported that learners often arrive late to classes due to the distance and location of their homes from school.

Table 4

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 7 Learners in the First and Second Quarters of the School Year 2024-2025

Variable	N	Mean	Interpretation
Academic Performance	102	82.71	Satisfactory

Table 4 presents the academic performance levels of Grade 7 learners in the first and second quarters of the 2024-2025 school year. The respondents obtained an overall rating of 82.71, interpreted as a satisfactory level.

The results suggest that there is still room for improvement in the performance of the majority of learners. Some learners miss quizzes and performance tasks due to tardiness, resulting in satisfactory performance only in the first and second quarters of the school year. The results align with those of Tani et al. (2019), who identified factors contributing to poor academic performance among learners. The effects of factors related to family obligations, work, social commitments, and financial concerns were examined. Results also showed a significant relationship between the academic performance of learners and their attendance.

Table 5

Level of Academic Performance of Grade 7 Learners in the First and Second Quarters of the School Year 2024-2025 when grouped according to sex, Number of Siblings, Distance from Home to School, and Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Categories	Mean	Interpretation
Sex	Male	80.71	Satisfactory
	Female	84.28	Satisfactory
Number of Siblings	Few	83.09	Satisfactory
	Many	82.51	Satisfactory
Distance From Home to School	Nearer	82.28	Satisfactory
	Farther	83.07	Satisfactory
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	80.80	Satisfactory
	Higher	83.50	Satisfactory

Table 5 presents the level of learners' academic performance when grouped according to sex, number of siblings, distance from home to school, and parents' highest educational attainment.

As presented in the table, the respondents only obtained a satisfactory level, regardless of their profile background. However, upon further analysis, a difference in mean scores was observed. Male respondents obtained a rating of 80.71, while females obtained 84.28. Respondents with a new sibling got a rating of 83.09, while respondents with many siblings got 82.51. Respondents who live near the school obtained a rating of 82.28, whereas those who live far from the school received 83.07. Moreover, respondents with parents who had lower educational attainment obtained a rating of 80.80, while respondents with parents who had higher educational attainment obtained a rating of 83.50.

This implies that female respondents performed better than male respondents; respondents with few siblings were slightly ahead compared to those with many siblings; respondents who lived far from school outperformed those who lived near school

academically; and respondents with higher educational backgrounds achieved better performance than their counterparts. The academic performance of learners may be influenced by various factors beyond their personal characteristics. It is a general belief that the backgrounds of learners, the learning environment, parental support, and the availability of learning resources are contributing factors that have the most significant influence on their academic performance (Rabia, Mubarak, Tallat, & Nasir, 2017).

Table 6

Difference in the Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners according to the Student-Related Factors when grouped according to Sex, Number of Siblings, Distance from Home to School, and Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	45	61.02	854.00	0.004	0.05	Significant
	Female	57	43.98				
Number of Siblings	Few	34	46.82	997.00	0.258	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	68	53.84				
Distance from Home to School	Nearer	47	50.94	1266.00	0.859	0.05	Not Significant
	Farther	55	51.98				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	30	63.50	720.00	0.008	0.05	Significant
	Higher	72	46.50				

Table 6 summarizes the inferential statistics on the difference in the degree to which factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners are student-related, when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed *p*-values for the variables' number of siblings' and 'distance from home to school' are 0.258 and 0.859, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners of student-related factors when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings and the distance from home to school” was accepted.

However, for variables sex and parents' highest educational attainment, the computed *p*-values are 0.004 and 0.008, respectively, which are all less than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners of student-related factors when grouped and compared according to sex and parents' highest educational attainment” was rejected.

The results imply that the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners varies according to student-related factors, sex, and parents' highest level of educational attainment. Most female learners were enthusiastic about attending school and rarely arrived late. Parents with higher educational backgrounds were highly supportive of their children, offering the necessary educational needs and attention to encourage early school attendance and prevent absenteeism. This study suggests that both gender and parental education levels play significant roles in influencing students' attitudes towards punctuality and attendance. Consequently, understanding these factors can help educators and parents develop targeted strategies to improve school

attendance among Grade 7 learners. The result is supported by that of Polvorido (2019), which revealed that students' tardiness varies when compared according to sex, parents' educational attainment, nutritional status, and Grade level.

Table 7

Difference in the Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners according to the Family-Related Factors when grouped and compared according to Sex, Number of Siblings, Distance from Home to School, and Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	45	59.86	906.50	0.011	0.05	Significant
	Female	57	44.90				
Number of Siblings	Few	34	45.25	943.50	0.131	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	68	54.63				
Distance from Home to School	Nearer	47	50.52	1246.50	0.757	0.05	Not Significant
	Farther	55	52.54				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	30	61.53	779.00	0.027	0.05	Significant
	Higher	72	47.32				

Table 7 presents the inferential statistics on the difference in the degree to which family-related factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed *p*-values for the variables' number of siblings' and 'distance from home to school' are 0.131 and 0.757, respectively, which are all greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners of family-related factors when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings and the distance from home to school” was accepted.

However, for variables sex and parents' highest educational attainment, the computed *p*-values are 0.011 and 0.027, respectively, which are all less than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners of family-related factors when grouped and compared according to sex and parents' highest educational attainment” was rejected.

The result indicates that the degree to which family-related factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners varies based on their sex and the highest educational attainment of their parents. Female respondents were more devoted to family, particularly to the household chores assigned by their parents, than male respondents. Additionally, respondents whose parents had higher educational attainment rarely missed school because their parents provided the necessary resources. This finding suggests that both gender and parental education level play significant roles in shaping students' attitudes and behaviors towards punctuality. Consequently, understanding these dynamics can help educators and parents address tardiness more effectively.

The finding aligns with that of Abdullah (2020), which reveals that tardiness among males was significantly higher than that of females. Learners' reasons for chronic absences were supported by their parents. However, they were opposed by their friends. Learners' tardiness and absenteeism hurt their academic performance.

Table 8

Difference in the Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners according to the School-Related Factors when grouped and compared according to Sex, Number of Siblings, Distance from Home to School, and Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	45	58.36	974.00	0.037	0.05	Significant
	Female	57	46.09				
Number of Siblings	Few	34	48.29	1047.00	0.439	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	68	53.10				
Distance from Home to School	Nearer	47	43.59	920.50	0.012	0.05	Significant
	Farther	55	58.26				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	30	64.83	680.00	0.003	0.05	Significant
	Higher	72	45.94				

Table 8 presents the inferential statistics on the difference in the degree to which school-related factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners when grouped and compared according to variables.

The computed *p*-value for the variable number of siblings is 0.439, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance and thus interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners of school-related factors when grouped and compared according to the number of siblings” was accepted.

However, for the variables sex, distance from home to school, and parents' highest educational attainment, the computed *p*-values are 0.037, 0.012, and 0.003, respectively, all of which are less than the 0.05 level of significance and are thus interpreted as significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners of school-related factors when grouped and compared according to sex, distance from home to school, and parents' highest educational attainment” was rejected.

The result implies that the degree to which school-related factors affect the tardiness of Grade 7 learners varies based on their sex, distance from home to school, and the highest educational attainment of their parents. Despite school-related issues, female learners who live far from school and have parents with higher educational backgrounds experienced less impact than their counterparts. This finding suggests that female students may possess stronger coping mechanisms or support systems that help them manage school-related challenges more effectively, particularly when faced with longer commutes and higher parental educational levels. As a result, their experiences of tardiness differ significantly from those of male students or those with less supportive backgrounds. The study by Sabado et al. (2024) reveals factors that affect school attendance. Findings indicate a consensus among respondents regarding the influence of institutional factors, including the school environment and transportation. However, the study concludes that the demographics of the respondents do not significantly affect the perceived factors influencing school attendance.

Table 9

Difference in the Level of Academic Performance of Grade 7 Learners when grouped and compared according to Sex, Number of Siblings, Distance from Home to School, and Parents' Highest Educational Attainment

Variable	Category	N	Mean	t-value	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Sex	Male	45	80.71	-3.911	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Female	57	84.28				
Number of Siblings	Few	34	83.09	0.567	0.573	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	68	82.51				
Distance from Home to School	Nearer	47	82.28	-0.810	0.420	0.05	Not Significant
	Farther	55	83.07				
Parents' Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	30	80.80	-02.901	0.005	0.05	Significant
	Higher	72	83.50				

Table 9 presents comparative statistics on the academic performance of Grade 7 learners, grouped and compared by sex, number of siblings, distance from home to school, and parents' highest educational attainment.

For the variables' number of siblings' and 'distance from home to school', the computed *p*-values are 0.000 and 0.005, respectively, which are both greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on the results, it was interpreted as not significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners when they are grouped and compared according to number of siblings and distance from home to school” was accepted.

However, for variables of sex and parents' highest education, the computed *p*-values are 0.000 and 0.005, respectively, which are less than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, they are interpreted as statistically significant. Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant difference in the level of academic performance of Grade 7 learners when they are grouped and compared according to sex and parents' highest educational attainment” was rejected.

The result implies that the academic performance levels of Grade 7 learners vary based on their sex and the highest educational attainment of their parents. This result suggests that sex and parents' highest educational attainment are favorable conjectures for academic performance. Females with parents who have higher educational backgrounds may perform better than their counterparts. The finding suggests that the educational environment and expectations set by parents can have a significant impact on the academic success of their children, particularly for females. Consequently, a supportive and well-educated family background may contribute to enhanced educational outcomes for girls in Grade 7. The finding is supported by Anhao (2022), which reveals a significant difference in the degree to which factors affect learners' academic performance when they are grouped and compared according to sex, parents' highest educational attainment, and average family monthly income.

Table 10

Relationship Between the Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners and the Level of Academic Performance

Variables	N	r	p-value	Level Significance	of Interpretation
-----------	---	---	---------	--------------------	-------------------

Degree of Factors Affecting the Tardiness of Grade 7 Learners	102	-0.640	.000	.005	Significant
Level of Academic Performance	102				

As presented in the table, the computed r was 0.6460 with a p -value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, it is interpreted as “significant.” Therefore, the hypothesis that states “there is no significant relationship between the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners and level of academic performance was therefore rejected.

The result suggests that the degree of factors affecting the tardiness of Grade 7 learners has a negative or decreasing effect on their academic performance. If a learner is consistently late, it can significantly impact academic performance due to missed classes or instructional hours. It may also result in not accomplishing homework, written exams, and projects. This habit may lead to more serious problems, like poor academic performance. The finding aligns with that of Abdullah (2020), who reported that tardiness and absenteeism hurt academic performance. The higher the level of student tardiness and absenteeism, the lower the chance of getting high Grades. Thus, student tardiness and absenteeism greatly affect students’ academic performance.

CONCLUSION

The study found that most respondents were female, had many siblings, lived far from school, and came from families with higher parental education. Overall, student-, family-, and school-related factors affecting tardiness were low, though male learners with many siblings and parents with lower education exhibited moderate levels. Academic performance of Grade 7 learners was generally satisfactory, with female learners whose parents had higher education performing better. Significant differences were observed in tardiness and academic performance based on sex, parents’ educational background, and distance from home to school, and a clear relationship existed between tardiness and academic performance. The findings suggest that learners’ enthusiasm mitigates the impact of personal, family, and school challenges on tardiness, though male learners with many siblings remain more prone to lateness, and overall academic performance still requires improvement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Consequently, it is recommended that schools implement interventions to address student-related factors through punctuality programs, support family-related factors via parent engagement and reduced household burdens, improve school-related factors by ensuring safety and flexible scheduling, and enhance academic performance through catch-up sessions, peer tutoring, and promoting disciplined study habits, while fostering a more equitable and supportive learning environment for all learners.

Acknowledgment

This endeavor would not have been possible without the invaluable support, guidance, and expertise of the university’s administration, advisers, and panel members who contributed to the development and completion of this study. Sincere gratitude is extended to the respondents for their time and cooperation, as well as to everyone who, in various ways, assisted in the realization of this work. Above all, gratitude is given to Divine Providence for providing guidance and inspiration throughout the research process.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that this research has no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

Abdullah, S. (2020). Causes of Tardiness, Absenteeism, and Academic Performance among Low-Performing Students of Esperanza National High School. *Journal of American Academic Research*, 8(1), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36704.30724>

Adegunju, K. A., Ola-Alani, E. K., & Agubossi, L. A. (2019). Factors Responsible for Students' Lateness to School, as Expressed by Nigerian Teachers in Elementary Schools. *Mimbar Sekolah Dasar*, 6(2), 185-197. doi:10.17509/mimbar-sd.v6i2.17040

- Ames, H., Glenton, C. & Lewin, S. (201). Purposive sampling in a qualitative evidence synthesis: a worked example from a synthesis on parental perceptions of vaccination communication. *BMC Med Res Methodol*, 19(26). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0665-4>
- Baier, D. (2016). The school as an influencing factor of truancy. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociology*. 5(1), 191-202. 10.6000/1929-4409.2016.05.18.
- Balkis, M. (2016). School absenteeism among high school students: Contributing factors. *Educational Sciences: Theory & Practice*, 16, 1819–1831. <https://doi.org/10.12738/estp.2016.6.0125>
- Bhur, P. (2018). The influence of the number of siblings on expected family size in a cohort of young adults in Germany. *Demographic Research*, 39(10), 315-338. DOI: 10.4054/DemRes.2018.39.10
- Carroll, M. (2021). Learning loss in the Covid-19 pandemic: teachers' views on the nature and extent of loss. *Research Matters: A Cambridge University Press & Assessment publication*, 34, 6-26.
- Chica-Olmo, J. (2018). Effect of distance from home to school and spatial dependence between homes on mode of commuting to school. *Journal of Transport Geography*. 72. 1-12. 10.1016/j.jtrangeo.2018.07.013.
- Collier, R. (2016). Problems at home contribute to truancy in JCPS schools. <http://www.wdrb.com/story/33915895/problems-at-home-contribute-to-truancy-in-jcps-schools>.
- Colinares, et al (2017). Factors Affecting Students' Absenteeism in Senior High School: Basis for Intervention. *Practical Research*. Atty. Orlando S. Remando National High School.
- Cromey, T. L., and Hanson, B.S. (2020). An exploratory analysis of school-based student assessment systems. Naperville, IL: North Central Regional Education Laboratory.
- Gano et al. (2024). Exploring the determinants of student tardiness in educational settings. *Global Scientific Journals*, 12(4), 66-79
- Goodwin, D. (2020). A comparative analysis of tardiness policies of elementary schools. *All Theses and Dissertations*. 311. <https://dune.une.edu/theses/311>
- Hamzar, A. (2020). Students' habit of tardiness to attend class. *International Journal of Indonesian Education and Teaching*, 4(2), 306-316. <https://doi.org/10.24071/ijiet.v4i2.2573>
- Hamza et al. (2020). Analysis of the factors causing students' absenteeism and its impact on students' academic performance at the elementary level in Quetta City. *Pakistan Journal of Educational Research*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.52337/pjer.v3i1.30>
- Harisha et al. (2016) Factors affecting school absenteeism and Tardiness and its effect to scholastic performance. *Asian Journal of Clinical Pediatrics and Neonatology*, 4(4), 10-14.
- Heale, R. (2015). Validity and reliability in quantitative studies. *Evidence-Based Nursing*; 18(1), 66-67.
- Jacob, B. & Lovett, K. (2017). Chronic absenteeism: An old problem in search of new answers. <https://www.brookings.edu/research/going-to-school-is-optional-schools-need-to-engage-students-to-increase-their-lifetime-opportunities/>.
- Kenny, D. A. (2019). Enhancing validity in psychological research. *American Psychologist*, 74(9), 1018–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000531>
- Komakech, R. A. & Osuu, J. R. (2014). Students' absenteeism: A silent killer of universal secondary education (use) in Uganda. *International Journal of IJiet* Vol. 4, No. 2, July 2020 314 *Education Research*, 2(10), 417-436. <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2014/October-2014/33.pdf>
- MacFarland, T.W., Yates, J.M. (2016). Mann–Whitney U Test. In: *Introduction to Nonparametric Statistics for the Biological Sciences Using R*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-30634-6_4
- Maile, S. & Olowoyo, M. M. (2017). The Causes of Late Arrival among High School Students in Soshanguve, Pretoria, South Africa. *Pedagogical Research*, 2(2), 4
- Majeed, A. (2019). Causes of Absenteeism among University Students. *European Academic Research*, 7(3).
- Komakech, R. A. & Osuu, J. R. (2014). Students' absenteeism: a silent killer of universal secondary education (use) in Uganda. *International Journal of Education Research* 4(2), 417-436. <https://www.ijern.com/journal/2014/October-2014/33.pdf>
- Moldero et al. (2024). Factors Affecting Tardiness and Absences: Basis for Intervention. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 12(6), 187-194. DOI: 10.12691/education-12-6-1
- Moore et al. (2021). A qualitative examination of the impacts of financial stress on college students' well-being: Insights from a large, private institution. *SAGE Open Med*, 9(1). doi: 20503121211018122.
- Navel, M. and Aquino, G. (2019). Administration and supervision for Philippine schools. Phoenix Publishing House Inc
- Ocak et al. (2017). The Causes of Absenteeism Among High School Students. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(4). doi:105281/zernodo.376841
- Odebode, A. A. (2019). Causes of Indiscipline Among Students as Viewed by Primary School Teachers in Nigeria. *Mimbar Sekolah Dasar*, 6(1), 126-134.
- Polvorido, R. (2019). Absenteeism and its relationship to academic performance of the learners: basis for intervention plan. Unpublished Master's Thesis. STI West Negros University.
- Qureshi, M.I., and Ahmad, A. (2019). Medical Students' Perspective on Absenteeism and Its Remedies. *Pak Armed Forces Med Journal*, 69(2):332-339. <https://pafmj.org/PAFMJ/article/view/2749>

- Sabado et al. (2024). Unraveling perceived factors affecting the school attendance of senior high school students. *Psych Educ*, 18(2): 111-122 doi:10.5281/zenodo.10850594
- Salao, F. (2021). Absenteeism and truancy among senior high school learners. *International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field*. 7(3), 239-246.
- Sahibzada, J. (2020). Students' self-confidence and its impacts on their learning process. *American International Journal of Social Science Research* 5(1).
[https:// www.cribfb.com/ journal/index.php/aijssr/article/download/462/663/](https://www.cribfb.com/journal/index.php/aijssr/article/download/462/663/).
- Siedlecki, Sandra L., PhD, RN, APRN-CNS, FAAN. Understanding Descriptive Research Designs and Methods. *Clinical Nurse Specialist* 34(1), 8-12. DOI: 10.1097/NUR.0000000000000493
- Taber, K. (2017). The use of Cronbach's alpha when developing and reporting research in instruments in science education. *Research in Science Education*
- Tison, A. C., Lachica, R., & Bautista, M. (2025). Factors Affecting Learners' Academic Performance. *International Multidisciplinary Journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability, and Excellence (IMJRISE)*, 2(6), 380-390.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15647419>
- Villaneva et al. (2023). Tardiness: Students' cases at Kawit National High School proposed intervention. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*. 8(5), 1291-1307
- Whitney, C. & Liu, J. (2017). What we're missing: A descriptive analysis of part-day absenteeism in secondary schools.
<https://cepa.stanford.edu/content/what-we%E2%80%99remissing-descriptive-analysis-part-day-absenteeism-secondary-school>.